

Oxidation of some thioacids by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate : A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : The oxidation of thioglycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acids by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC) is first order both in TEACC and thioacids. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen ion dependence has taking the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of thiolactic acid has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analysed by using Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. A mechanism involving the formation of a thioester and its decomposition in slow step has been proposed.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, halochromate, oxidation, thioacids.

Introduction

Specific and selective oxidation of organic compounds under non-aqueous conditions is an important reaction in synthetic organic chemistry. For this a number of different chromium(VI) derivatives have been reported¹⁻⁵. Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC) is also one such compound used for the oxidation benzyl alcohols⁶. There seems to be no report on the oxidation aspects using tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC). We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and several studies by halochromates have already been reported⁷⁻¹⁰. In the present paper, we report the kinetics of the oxidation of thioglycolic (TGA), thiolactic (TLA) and thiomalic (TMA) acids by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. Mechanistic aspects are also discussed.

Results and discussion

The reactions are of first order with respect to TEACC. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of TEACC. The reaction is first order with respect to thioacid also (Table 1). The oxidation of thioacids by TEACC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus a one electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of thioacids by TEACC at 298 K

10 ³ [TEACC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Thioacid] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)		
		TGA	TLA	TMA
1.0	0.10	1.68	7.83	4.14
1.0	0.20	3.48	16.0	8.10
1.0	0.40	6.70	31.5	16.5
1.0	0.60	10.8	47.7	24.0
1.0	0.80	14.0	65.0	32.4
1.0	1.00	17.1	79.2	39.6
2.0	0.40	6.21	32.4	16.2
4.0	0.40	5.85	29.7	17.1
6.0	0.40	7.20	30.6	15.3
8.0	0.40	6.30	29.0	17.8
1.0	0.20	3.69 ^a	17.1 ^a	9.27 ^a

^aContained 0.001 M acrylonitrile.

The rates of oxidation of three thioacids were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 3). The hydrogen ion dependence has the following form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and b , for TLA, are $6.11 \pm 0.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $10.7 \pm 0.04 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9953$). The oxidation of thiolactic acid was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of TEACC and its reac-

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of thioacid by TEACC

TA	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
TGA	9.54	17.1	31.5	56.7	42.8 ± 0.7	-135 ± 2	83.0 ± 0.5
TLA	46.8	79.2	135	225	37.4 ± 0.4	-141 ± 1	79.3 ± 0.4
TMA	22.5	39.6	72.0	126	41.4 ± 0.6	-133 ± 2	81.0 ± 0.5

Table 3. Effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the oxidation of thioacids by TEACC

[TEACC] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [thioacids] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³,
Temp. = 298 K

[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)					
	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
TGA	19.8	23.1	30.0	33.1	42.2	47.7
TLA	92.7	108	135	157	189	220
TMA	45.0	54.9	67.5	79.0	97.8	108

tion with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values k_2 at 298 K are recorded in Table 4. The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other one is acid-dependent.

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of thioacetic acid by TEACC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Solvents	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	22.4	Toluene	7.94
1,2-Dichloroethane	27.5	Acetophenone	38.0
Dichloromethane	23.4	THF	14.8
DMSO	79.2	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	8.32
Acetone	25.1	1,4-Dioxane	12.9
DMF	41.7	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	6.61
Butanone	18.2	Carbon disulfide	4.27
Nitrobenzene	33.9	Acetic acid	2.82
Benzene	9.77	Ethyl acetate	11.2
Cyclohexane	1.12		

The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of TEACC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (2).

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PBC⁹ and MCC¹⁰.

The rate constants of the oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen

solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (LESR) of Kamlet and Taft¹¹ (2).

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (2)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (2), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (3)–(6).

$$\log k_2 = -4.11 + 1.65 (\pm 0.20) \pi^* + 0.19 (\pm 0.17) \beta + 0.27 (\pm 0.16) \alpha \quad (3)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8680; sd = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.40$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.17 + 1.74 (\pm 0.20) \pi^* + 0.10 (\pm 0.17) \beta \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8413; sd = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.42$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.15 + 1.77 (\pm 0.19) \pi^* \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8375; sd = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.15 + 0.41 (\pm 0.38) \beta \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0676; sd = 0.46; n = 18; \psi = 0.99$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹².

Kamlet's¹¹ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 87% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹² the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eq. (4)). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 84% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's¹³ eq. (7) of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (7)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in

terms of eq. (7), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.46 + (\pm 0.04) A + 1.79 (\pm 0.03) B - 4.32 \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9962; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.20 (\pm 0.29) A - 3.09 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0070; sd = 0.48; n = 19; \psi = 0.91$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.76 (\pm 0.09) B - 4.17 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9614; sd = 0.09; n = 19; \psi = 0.20$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.35 \pm 0.17 (A + B) - 4.27 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7840; sd = 0.22; n = 19; \psi = 0.48$$

The rates of oxidation of TLA in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* eq. (8)) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 99% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 78% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 78% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the

relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5300$; $sd = 0.33$; $\psi = 0.70$).

Mechanism : The lack of any effect of radical scavenger such as acrylonitrile on the reaction rate and the failure to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile point against the operation of a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals. The observed solvent effect supports a transition state, which is more polar than the reactant state. In the oxidation of thioacids by PCC^{14} , PFC^{15} and QFC^{16} , a Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics were observed and the formation of a thioester as an intermediate and its subsequent decomposition in slow step was proposed. In the present reaction, although there is no kinetic evidence for the formation of thioester, its formation in small amounts cannot be ruled out. It is, therefore, proposed that this reaction also involves the formation of an ester intermediate in a pre-equilibrium but that the equilibrium constant has a small value (eqs. (12)–(15)). Alternatively, the reaction may involve a direct transfer of a hydride ion from the S–H group to the oxidant (eq. (16)) followed by the reactions (14) and (15).

Scheme 1

The formation of a sulphenium cation, in the rate-determining step, is supported by the observed major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

It is of interest to compare here the reaction patterns of the oxidation of thioacids by PFC¹⁵, QFC¹⁶, BPCC¹⁷, MCC¹⁸ and the present oxidant. PFC and QFC represented a Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics with respect to thioacid, whereas the oxidation by MCC and TEACC exhibited a second order kinetics, first with respect to each reactant. This may be due to a very low value of the formation constant of the thioester. The solvent effect and hydrogen ion dependence are parallel in all the reactions.

Materials and methods :

The thioacids (Fluka) and dithiodiglycollic acid (Evan Chemicals, USA) were commercial products and were used as such. Dithiodimalic and dithiodilactic acids were prepared by the oxidation of the corresponding thiols by ferric alum¹⁹. The solutions of the thioacids were freshly prepared in DMSO and were standardized by titrating them against a standard solution of iodine^{19,20}. TEACC was prepared by the reported method⁶ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. The solvents were purified by usual methods²¹.

Stoichiometry : Stoichiometric determinations, as well as the characterization of the products, carried out polarographically^{22,23} using an automatic (Heyrovsky TP 55A). It was found that the cathode wave given by a known sample of disulphide dimmer coincided by the wave given by the final product of the oxidation. The reaction exhibited a 1 : 2 stoichiometry, i.e. 2 moles of the thiol are oxidized per mole of TEACC reduced. Further, the reaction mixtures with an excess of TEACC were allowed to go to completion and the residual TEACC was determined iodometrically. These results also gave a 1 : 2 stoichiometry. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, is 3.95 ± 0.15 .

Thus TEACC undergoes a two electron change. This is in accord with the earlier observations with other halochromates⁷⁻¹⁰. It has already been shown that both PFC²⁴ and PCC²⁵ act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species, by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility,

ESR and IR studies.

Kinetic measurement : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the thioacids over TEACC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were carried out in flasks blackend from the outside to prevent any photochemical reactions and were followed up to *ca.* 80% conversion by monitoring the decrease in the [TEACC] at 365 nm on a spectrophotometer (AIMIL, India, Model MK-II). The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear least-squares plots of $\log [TEACC]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants were evaluated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{obs}/[\text{reductant}]$.

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